

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF TRANSLATION THEORY

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Annotation : In this article, information about the theory of translation and its origin is presented and discussed

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In the Uzbek literature of the period of independence, along with all types and genres, growth and changes are clearly visible in the practice of literary translation. Again, it is a good thing that the translation from the original language is being traced. The fact that these young people are testing their talent and starting to read the literature of the Eastern and Western nations directly in our mother tongue raises great hopes.

At the same time, he is also taking the initiative to translate masterpieces of Uzbek literature into languages. The result of this work was that the Department of Literary Translation and International Relations under the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan established the "School of Young Translators" in cooperation with universities in the capital and regions that support young artists in our republic. it can be seen in the example of the first translated works being published in "Adib" publishing house, the regular publication of "Jahon Liyatari" magazine and many other products. After all, it is no secret that the honorable task of translating the examples of Uzbek literature into foreign languages and the masterpieces of world literature into our mother tongue depends on the talent and enthusiasm of today's generation.

Until the 20th century, the word "translation" was used only for the translation of historical, philosophical, literary and artistic works. In relation to the interpreter, the term "tilmoch" is used in Turkic peoples, "dolmetechen" in German, and "interpreter" in English and French. The general statement about the theory of translation has gained meaning in this regard. The first studies devoted to the theory of translation began to appear in the 20s and 30s of the last century. In the books of Amos, Postget, Finkel, Alekseev published during this period, and in Sanjar Siddiq's pamphlet "The Art of Literary Translation" (1936), we find theses that recognize the theory of translation as a science. In the 1950s, after the publication of articles on the theory of translation by the famous translator Ivan Kashkin and the linguist

Reformatsky, debates in this field began. Professor Reformatsky put forward the idea that "although the practice of translation serves all disciplines, the theory of translation cannot be an independent science, but can only be a branch of linguistics." After that, a number of studies and articles were published that approved and criticized them. 1953 –The International Association of Translators (FIT) was founded. Since 1955, its organ "Babil" (Babel) –magazine has been published.

Later, the studies of world scientists devoted to the problems of translation theory and translation criticism were published one after another. This determined the development of scientific research of scientists. By the 70s of the last century, an independent science called translation studies was formed in world philology.

Scholars such as Jumaniyaz Sharipov, Ninel Vladimirova, Gaybulla Salomov, Najmiddin Komilov, and Qudrat Musaev have made a great contribution to the development of translation studies in Uzbekistan. Today, the Uzbek translation school is recognized in the world translation science. Over the past twenty years, dozens of rare examples of Eastern literature have been translated into Uzbek. If until the 80s of the last century, most of such works were translated through the Russian language, and the Uzbek people got acquainted with examples of Eastern literature in the shade of indirect translations, since the 90s, more attention has been paid to direct translation from Eastern languages. began to be given. During this period, the work of translating samples of Uzbek literature into Eastern languages rose to a new level. The works of Cholpon, Abdulla Kadiri, Oibek, Gafur Ghulam, Pirimkul Kadirov, Adil Yakubov, Said Ahmed, Shukrullo, Otkir Hashimov and other writers were translated into Eastern languages such as Turkish, Chinese, Arabic, and Korean. Nevertheless, the number of works translated from Uzbek into Eastern languages is much less than the translations from Eastern languages. The reason for this, in my opinion, is the small number of local experts who translate Uzbek works into foreign languages. If we consider this as an example of translations from Uzbek and Turkish languages, we can see that until today, the works of Uzbek writers translated into Turkish have been translated by Turkish translators. This can also be said about translations into other languages. The translator's work is never secondary should not be understood. His work is equal to the work of a writer. The famous aphorism of the great Humboldt "language is activity". applies more to translators than anyone else. Translators moves the tongue. His work turned the language into a source of activity, and turns activity into a source of language. Already the work of the translator therefore, the treasures of your language are new words, terms, expressions, sentences with strange,

unprecedented, untested syntactic constructions, get rich The language is renewed due to the creative work of the translator.

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